

NOVEL INTERLAYERS FOR SELF-HEALING SANDWICH STRUCTURES

P B S Bailey, S A Hayes, A D Lafferty
Composite Systems Innovation Centre,
Kroto Research Institute, University of Sheffield, Broad Lane, Sheffield, S3 7HQ
p.bailey@sheffield.ac.uk

SUMMARY

A novel self-healing system is introduced for composite sandwich structures, based on an interlayer with adhesive and gap filling properties. A demonstration of principle is given with results of some initial mechanical tests.

Self-healing, Composite, Sandwich, Impact

INTRODUCTION

Sandwich composites are already an essential part of structural design, with ever expanding interest, particularly in the transport sector. While they offer great benefits, the fact remains that sandwich composites are highly susceptible to impact damage, but difficult to repair. Effects and repair schemes have been well documented in many specific scenarios and in broader texts such as Abrate [1].

The mechanical damage caused by an impact almost universally comprises three aspects: skin fracture; skin disbond; core crushing. Standard repair schemes as a minimum require the replacement of an entire section of front face and core. It is argued that such a degree of time and expense is not always warranted or even possible for minor damage in many applications. This research seeks to offer an alternative solution by building in the ability to conduct a simple, noninvasive repair, hereafter referred to as “healing”.

A variety of approaches are being considered [2,3,4] to modify existing fibre reinforced skin systems to embody a self-healing capability, focusing largely on solid structures based on pre-impregnated fibre material. Nonetheless, in a sandwich structure, theory clearly indicates that a good deal of the structural strength may be regained by reattaching the skin to the core, to prevent buckling. Other researchers have successfully demonstrated this effect by entirely different means [5]. Furthermore, all of the aforesaid healing systems for fibre reinforced resin systems can only repair closed or very narrow cracks. The concept presented here will be complementary since it would provide a closing pressure, improving the efficiency of any self-healing process

contained exclusively in the skin.

Novel interlayer materials are demonstrated which can fill the void left by core crushing and reinstate adhesion between skin and core. Following impact damage, the repairing function is activated by moderate heating of the affected area to a point above service temperature, causing local volume expansion and flow of the interlayer material. The interlayer material can be processed at low to moderate temperature and easily incorporated (for example laid up as a part-cured sheet, or sprayed *in situ*) as the structure is assembled, replacing any other adhesive used between core and skin.

This paper presents some initial mechanical tests showing the efficacy of this approach. The manufacture and composition of the interlayer material cannot be discussed at present.

EXPERIMENTAL

Initial Demonstration Pieces

The original proof of concept for the interlayer was conducted by impact, and subsequent healing, of single sided samples. Samples were produced by bonding 50kg/m³ poly(methacrylimide) foam core material (Rohacell IG51), to a flat sheet of [0°,90°] symmetric, carbon fibre reinforced epoxy (Cycom 977-2), previously cured according to specification, in an autoclave. The interlayer thickness was typically 1.5mm. Tests showed that an infrared heat lamp, at close range, provided sufficient heating power to activate the “healing” effect. Furthermore, using this method, a simple mask of aluminium foil provided adequate shielding to protect areas which did not require activation.

The test face was subjected to a impact energies of 3J, 5J and 7J, using a drop tower with a 12.5mm hemispherical indenter. In each case, two impacts of the same energy were created adjacent to one another; one was healed, the other left untreated. These were photographed, and later cross-sectioned using a diamond saw.

Four-point Bending

Strips of core foam (as before) were cut to 48mm x 250mm x 18mm, and a channel 0.5mm deep by 32mm wide machined into one side of each running just short of the entire length. Interlayer material was cast into the channels; one large batch was used for all the samples. 2 plies of 450g/m² chopped fibre E-glass mat were wet laid with polyester resin (Crystic 272) onto both faces of each sample, then cured for 16 hours at 50°C. These samples were necessarily produced in small batches; in order to minimise effects of variation between batches, each batch was distributed between the test types.

Sample edges were trimmed using a diamond saw to remove excess resin, leaving 45mm wide samples. Of these, 15 good samples were used for testing; undamaged,

impacted at their midpoint, and impacted then healed. Impact took the form of two 5.3J impacts side by side, using a 12.5mm hemispherical indenter. Healing consisted of exposing a 20mm strip at the centre of the specimen (using foil masks as before), to a 3kW infrared lamp, at a range of 450mm from the lamp, for 3 minutes.

Four-point bend tests were conducted in accordance with ASTM C393 using a support separation of 160mm and loading point separation of 40mm. Loading points were applied to the sample face embodying healing capability, rendering this side of the beam in compression. Crosshead speed was set at the minimum of 5mm/minute.

RESULTS

Initial Demonstrations

Activation of the healing layer pushed the skin back up to its original level, even for very severe impact damage. In the same set of tests, barely visible damage was completely removed by the “healing” process. Figure 1 is a photograph of the impacted surface, illustrating the fact that with a reasonably thick interlayer even the most severe damage, verging on complete perforation, can be pushed out.

Figure 1: Severe impact damage with and without activation of healing layer
[impact energy of 7J]

These samples were cross-sectioned using a diamond saw, but the contrast between interlayer and core material was poor. A better demonstration of the physical effect of the healing may be seen in Figure 2. A prototype sample for four point bend test was impacted at two locations, one of which was healed, then both were cross sectioned. At this point the interlayer composition had been modified to include a low concentration of black pigment, providing both contrast with other materials and colour change upon healing.

Here it can clearly be seen (in the left hand image) that the impact has permanently deformed a volume of the core and disbonded the skin over a considerably wider area, yet left little apparent damage on the surface. After healing (on the right) the interlayer has expanded, filling the roughly conical indentation and re-bonding to the skin.

Figure 2: Impact sites on polyester skinned panel; (left) as impacted, and (right) after healing.

Four-point Bend Tests

On the basis of the peak load values the results are encouraging, but have a severe degree of scatter, as may be seen in Figure 3. All samples failed by skin disbond followed by core shear fracture. Based on the mean values, it appears that the strength after impact is just over 60% of the original, but after healing it has returned to 85% of original.

Figure 3: Peak load in 4 point bending; mean (bar) and specimens (+)

Examining the plots of load vs displacement by batch (Figure 4), it becomes apparent

that there is considerable variation between batches. In general, the difference between undamaged and impacted specimens is comparable, but much less so with the healed samples.

Figure 4: Load vs displacement plots by batch
(solid line = undamaged; dashed = impacted; dotted = healed)

The fact that the first batch of specimens are particularly weak, to the extent that the healed sample was stronger than the undamaged, leads to a question over aging effects in the samples. It is proposed that there may be a weakening of the bond between skin and interlayer, due to styrene elution from the polyester resin. Upon healing the bond is reformed over much of that region which is particularly critical in this test geometry; for older samples in which the bond is significantly weakened this would improve the beam strength, yet for the newest samples in which little deterioration has occurred the healing process leaves a slightly weaker bond. This would also seem to agree with the fact that there is far less scatter in the peak load for healed samples.

These results represent interim testing to acquire some initial quantitative data. Further tests using commercially available, glass reinforced, epoxy prepreg skin materials are ongoing.

CONCLUSION

Standard repair schemes are extremely invasive and onerous. In many applications these are not cost effective, and in some cases the repaired structure may still be compromised. Initial results appear encouraging for this novel concept offering self-healing (ie. non-invasive repair) of sandwich structures for minor damage and in complex shapes and locations where current repair schemes could not be implemented. This system will be complementary to other ongoing developments in self-healing fibre reinforced resins used for skin materials.

REFERENCES

- [1] "Impact on Composite Structures", S Abrate, *Cambridge University Press*, 1998.
- [2] "Self-healing of damage in fibre-reinforced polymer-matrix composites"; Hayes SA, Zhang W, Braithwaite M, Jones FR, *Journal of the Royal Society: Interface*, Vol.4, Iss.13, p381-387 (2007).
- [3] "A hollow fibre reinforced polymer composite encompassing self-healing and enhanced damage visibility"; Pang JWC, Bond IP, *Composites Science and Technology*, Vol.65, Iss.11, p1791-1799 (2005).
- [4] "Full recovery of fracture toughness using a nontoxic solvent-based self-healing system"; Caruso MM, Blaiszik BJ, White SR, Sottos NR, Moore JS, *Advanced Functional Materials*, Vol.18, Iss.13, p1898-1904 (2008).
- [5] "Self-healing sandwich panels: Restoration of compressive strength after impact"; Williams HR, Trask RS, Bond IP, *Composites Science and Technology*, Vol.68, Iss.16, p3171-3177 (2008).